

ASSESSMENT OF INTERFACIAL ADHESION BETWEEN CARBON FIBER AND EPOXY BY TRANSVERSE FIBER BUNDLE AND SINGLE FIBER FRAGMENTATION TESTS

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ABSTRACT

This work concentrates on contrasting interfacial normal strength (INS) and interfacial shear strength (ISS) results separately from the transverse fiber bundle (TFB) test and traditional microscopic test and analyzing the similarities and differences for these two test approaches. Four kinds of carbon fibers were employed to prepare specimens with the same epoxy resin. The interfacial properties of these fiber-matrix system were investigated by both the TFB test and single fiber fragmentation (SFF) test. For the TFB test, the multiscale approach based on the highly efficient Generalized Method of Cells (GMC) was adopted to describe the failure and interphase behavior of TFBC specimen. The macroscopic structural level for the TFBC was discretized by the FE method using Abaqus. In the GMC micromechanics model, a discrete interphase was included apart from the fiber and matrix. The progressive failure process was simulated and the micro interfacial stress was exported for discussion. The INS was successfully determined by the correlation of the experimental and analytical results. For the SFF test, the fragmentation method was combined with acoustic emission (AE) analysis and the IFS was calculated based on the classic Kelly-Tyson model. Furthermore, the IFS results from the SFF test and the INS results from the TFB test were contrasted. Both tests show the same trend, but differs in the specific values. The coefficient of variation (CV) of TFB test was much lower than that of SFF test. The TFB test may be an alternative for the assessment of interfacial strength.

1 INTRODUCTION

Since the fiber–matrix interface plays a critical role in determining the performance of fiber-reinforced composites, increasing efforts have been devoted to develop techniques for characterizing the adhesion between the fiber and surrounding polymer matrix over the last few decades. It is well acknowledged that most techniques, such as push-out test, fragmentation test, pull-out test and micro droplet test have been intended to directly determine interfacial shear strength (IFS) at the single filament level. Meanwhile, the macroscopic mechanical properties of composite laminates, such as short beam shear strength and transverse tensile strength, have also been employed to indirectly evaluate the interfacial properties.

Recently the transverse fiber bundle composite (TFBC) has been designed to characterize interfacial bonding strength^[1-5]. The TFBC is a dog-bone tension specimen containing a fiber bundle which is perpendicular to the transverse loading direction. The tensile test results of the TFBC were found very sensitive to slight changes in the carbon fiber/epoxy interface. TFB test can provide a simple and quick approach for the assessment of fiber–matrix adhesion, especially in the fiber radical direction.

Okoroafor and Hill firstly addressed the TFB tension method to reduce composite fracture mechanisms to occur mainly at the interface^[2]. Later Ageorges et al. found that carbon/epoxy TFB results are very sensitive to carbon fibres with different surface treatments^[3]. And TFB transverse strength showed the same trend with the results of both the single-fibre Broutman compression fragmentation tests and unidirectional composite transverse tensile tests. Drescher et al. also found a good correlation between the results of the TFB test and the single fibre pull-out test with the corresponding carbon fiber specimen^[4].

However, TFBC tensile strength is not simply equal to the fiber/matrix interfacial strength. Theoretical analysis is necessary for establishing quantitative relationship between the TFB tensile strength and interfacial strength. An efficient multiscale model was employed to analyse the TFB test theoretically in our earlier work^[5]. In order to better understand the newly developed testing approach, the direct contrast between interfacial normal strength (INS) and interfacial shear strength (ISS) results separately from the transverse fiber bundle (TFB) test and traditional microscopic test is still urged.

In this work, both the TFB test and single fiber fragmentation (SFF) test were used to determine the interfacial properties of carbon fiber and epoxy. For the TFB test, a multiscale model based on the highly efficient Generalized Method of Cells (GMC) was adopted to describe the failure and interphase behavior of TFBC specimen during tension process. The INS was determined by the combination of the experimental and analytical results. For the SFF test, the fragmentation method was combined with acoustic emission (AE) analysis and the IFS was calculated based on the classic Kelly-Tyson model. Furthermore, the IFS results from the SFF test and the INS results from the TFB test were contrasted.

2 THEORETICAL ASPECTS OF TFB TEST

The multiscale model for the TFB test (Figure 1) has been successfully been used to describe the tension process of TFBC. For the macro model was created using the commercial finite element software Abaqus. The residual stress in this work was assumed to be generated only during the thermal cooling procedure from glass transition temperature T_g to the ambient temperature (20 °C). A temperature field was established in the FE model and the residual stress was calculated for the TFBC. After thermal cooling, a transverse displacement in the OY direction was applied at the parallel end of the resin to simulate tensile loading. Furthermore, the Generalized Method of Cells (GMC) reformulated by Pindera et al.^[6] was implemented as the micro model. A discrete interphase was considered in the micro GMC model apart from the fiber and the matrix. The failure of matrix is assumed to occur if one of the micro strains exceeds the corresponding allowable strain. The interphase damage is assumed to initiate by the maximum stress criterion.

Figure 1: Multiscale model for TFB tension test.

Eventually, the GMC model, together with the failure criteria was written in a FORTRAN code and implemented into the FE model as a user-defined subroutine. During the analysis, the micro stresses were calculated at the Gauss integration points for each time increment and examined for damage detection using the failure criteria. Once either failure criterion was satisfied, the stiffness reduction of the corresponding constituent properties in the RUC was applied for the next increment analysis. At the same time, the stiffness of macro FE elements was also degraded to a near zero value to simulate the initiation of damage. With the load gradually increasing, the damage would propagate. The process would not be terminated until the damage propagated through the whole composite layer. The macro stress-strain curves and micro stresses were exported for further discussion.

3 THEORETICAL ASPECTS OF SFF TEST

In the SFF test, the interfacial shear strength τ is traditionally calculated via the Kelly–Tyson equation

$$\tau = \frac{3}{8} \frac{d_f \sigma_f}{l_c} \quad (1)$$

where d_f is the fiber diameter and l_c is the saturation length measured at the saturation limit, which is reached at the end of the fragmentation test when no more fiber breaks occur. σ_f is the strength of a fiber segment of length equal to the saturation length. The value of the fiber fragment strength at the saturation length may then be obtained:

$$\sigma_f = \sigma_0 \left(\frac{4}{3} l_c / l_0 \right)^{-\frac{1}{m}} \quad (2)$$

where σ_0 is the average stress of a fiber fragment of length l_0 .

4 EXPERIMENTAL

4.1 Materials

Four kinds of carbon fiber were used in the experiment: Toray T800H and T700S and domestic JHT800 and MT700. The diglycidyl ether of bisphenol A (DGEBA, Dow Chemical Company) with an epoxide equivalent weight of 185-192 g/eq was mixed with curing agent D400 (Dow Chemical Company).

4.2 TFB test

The carbon fiber bundle was employed to prepare the TFB specimen. Firstly, a length of fiber bundle was cut down and stretched directly. The stretched bundle was placed in the middle narrow slit of the mold and kept under tension. The degassed resin was then casted into the mold. TFB samples were finally cured in 3 steps: 75 °C for 2 hours, 110 °C for 2 hours and 150 °C for 2 hours. After being demolded, the specimens were milled on the surfaces using sandpapers to reduce surface roughness, which ensured the cross-section in the middle of the gage length only contain the fiber bundle (Figure 2a).

Figure 2: Typical TFB specimen and SFF specimen.

The TFB and bulk epoxy tension tests were conducted on a universal test machine (Instron 5565) using a 500N load cell. The cross-head speed was 1 mm/min. The elongation of specimen during tension was accurately measured by the extensometer with a gauge length of 25 mm.

4.3 SFF test

Single-fiber fragmentation composite specimens (Figure 2b) were prepared for testing. Mechanical tests were performed with acoustic emission (AE) analysis and the stress-strain curves were recorded in real-time. Debond lengths were measured on a video monitor using a video micrometer. Data required for the Kelly-Tyson analysis were the number of breaks in the fiber and the corresponding applied stress and strain for the specimen over the complete loading history.

5 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

5.1 Analysis results of TFB test

The tensile strength of T800H/epoxy TFB specimen is 39.7 ± 4.9 MPa. In the tension process, the neat epoxy began yielding at the strain of 3% and eventually ruptured at the strain of about 9% after necking in the gauge length. Nevertheless, no plastic deformation was observed in the TFB test. Failure suddenly occurred as soon as the maximum strain was reached. The elastic modulus of the TFB specimen altered little compared with the neat epoxy, which indicates that the inserted fiber bundles does not greatly affect the tensile behavior in the elastic stage, but play a significant role in deciding the failure of the TFB composite.

Figure 3 (a-d) shows the progressive damage process of the TFB specimen with a weak interphase under transverse tensile loading. In the composite layer, the red elements denote the failure regions while the intact regions are indicated with blue elements. The interfacial failure started at the free edge (Figure 3 (a)) of the fiber bundle and then propagated (Figure 3 (b) and (c)). Eventually the damages spread all over the composite layer (Figure 3 (d)), which is consistent with the observation result of fracture surface.

Figure 3: Progressive failure process of TFB tension test.

Figure 4 plots the interfacial normal stress of the representative element as a function of the circumferential coordinate θ for T800H/epoxy TFB specimen. The interfacial normal stress is the dominated interfacial stress component which determines the interfacial damage of the representative element. This also validates the assumption of and is the most critical parameter of the interphase failure criterion.

Figure 4: Interfacial normal stress result for T700S and T800H TFB specimen.

5.2 Contrast of two approaches

The precise value of interfacial normal strength was adjusted until the experimental and predicted values of σ_{TFB} were equivalent. In Figure 5, the interfacial normal strength is more than twice the value of measured TFB tensile strength. The interfacial normal strength of T800H/epoxy TFB specimen is 16.3 MPa higher than that of T700S/epoxy TFB specimen while the gap of σ_{TFB} is only 10.4 MPa. Since the micro model can give more realistic results, the calculated interfacial normal strength should be used for more accurate evaluation of interfacial bonding strength in the TFB test.

Furthermore, the difference of the longitudinal interfacial shear strength of the same carbon fiber determined from the single fiber fragmentation test. Both tests show the same trend, but differs in the specific values. The coefficient of variation (CV) of TFB test was much lower than that of SFF test. If combined with multiscale failure analysis, the TFB test may be an alternative for characterizing the fiber/matrix bonding strength.

Figure 5: Contrast of interfacial adhesion of strength.

6 CONCLUSIONS

The TFB test is a quick, simple and reliable approach for characterizing interfacial normal strength. The multiscale approach based on the GMC micromechanics model provides an efficient analysis for the TFB test. The micro interfacial strength can be determined by the combination of the experimental and multiscale analysis results. The calculated interfacial normal strength rather than TFB tensile strength should be used for more accurate evaluation of fiber/matrix bonding strength. The characterisation of the fibre/matrix bonding with the TFB test presents a quick and cost-effective analysis tool, compared to the SFF test.

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REFERENCES

- [1] Jiang Z, Zhang H, Zhang Z, Murayama H, Okamoto K. Improved bonding between PAN-based carbon fibers and fullerene-modified epoxy matrix. *Compos Part A-Appl S*, **39**, 2008, pp.1762-1767.
- [2] EU Okoroafor, R Hill. Determination of fiber-resin interface strength in fiber-reinforced plastics using the acoustic emission technique. *J. Phys D: Appl Phys*, **28**, 1995, pp.1816.
- [3] C Ageorges, K Friedrich, L Ye. Experiments to relate carbon-fiber surface treatments to composite mechanical properties. *Compos Sci Technol*, **59**, 1999, pp. 2101-2113.
- [4] Drescher P, Thomas M, Borris J, Riedel U, Arlt C. Strengthening fiber/matrix interphase by fiber surface modification and nanoparticle incorporation into the matrix. *Compos Sci Technol*, **74**, 2013, pp. 60-66.
- [5] G Qi, S Du, B Zhang, Z Tang, Y Yu. Evaluation of carbon fiber/epoxy interfacial strength in transverse fiber bundle composite: Experiment and multiscale failure modeling. *Compos Sci Technol*, **105**, 2014, pp. 1-8.
- [6] M-J Pindera, BA Bednarczyk. An efficient implementation of the generalized method of cells for unidirectional, multi-phased composites with complex microstructures. *Compos Part B-Eng*, **30**, 1999, pp. 87-105.